

Printed Integrated Logic Circuits Based on Chitosan-Gated Organic Transistors for Future Edible Systems

Giulia Coco, Valerio Francesco Annese, Valerio Galli, Ilaria Penna, Debora Russo, Marina Veronesi, Rita Scarpelli, Stefania Sabella, and Mario Caironi*

Edible electronics made of materials that can be safely ingested is researched for applications in food monitoring, drug delivery, and gastrointestinal tract screening, addressing sustainability and e-waste concerns. Edible electronics can also endow future edible robots with sensing and control. In this work, the realization of building blocks of future edible computing units is tackled. Potentially edible unipolar NOT and NAND logic gates, as well as a ring oscillator, based on an inkjet-printed, p-type electrolyte-gated organic transistor, are demonstrated. Food additives and derivatives are used for electrodes, passivation layers, and the electrolyte. A well-known biocompatible conjugated polymer is printed in the micrograms range to form the transistors active layer and the load resistors. A cascade *in vitro* digestion assay applied to the transistors do not reveal adverse effects on an intestinal cell epithelium model. The transistor is optimized for operation at low voltage and for low leakage, allowing the logic circuits to operate below 0.7 V, compatibly with recently developed edible energy sources. These results demonstrate the possibility of realizing low-voltage logic circuitry with scalable fabrication approaches exploiting potentially edible functional materials, moving toward future control electronics for food monitoring and healthcare.

monitoring, and remotely controlled systems for precise drug delivery^[2] are some examples of the incoming digital revolution in these sectors. All of these scenarios share a common factor: direct or potential interaction with the human body, which raises a safety issue that ingestible systems partially address. While being powerful biomedical probes, attracting increasing research and technological interests,^[3] ingestible devices have a small but finite risk of retention, posing limits to unsupervised administration, and may require post-performance recollection. Moreover, in the case of single-use and disposable devices, their electronic parts would soon become e-waste, having a high impact on the environment.^[4]

To overcome these limits, edible electronics has been proposed as a novel research field that leverages the electronic properties of food additives and food-derived materials to fabricate circuits safe for ingestion and contact with food.^[5] After performing their functions, ingested edible devices

could be metabolized, digested, or simply evacuated to be degraded in the environment without contributing to e-waste. Edible electronic circuits could be used as standalone devices or paired with edible sensors and actuators to fabricate edible robots or robotic food that could perform complex functions inside and outside the body.^[6] Edible electronics is expected to enable

1. Introduction

The interest in electronic devices that could monitor important parameters in areas such as food quality and healthcare is rapidly increasing. Labels tracking temperature, pH, and gases for food spoilage prevention,^[1] smart pills for gastrointestinal (GI) tract

G. Coco, V. F. Annese, V. Galli, M. Caironi
Center for Nano Science and Technology
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Rubattino 81, Milano 20134, Italy
E-mail: mario.caironi@iit.it

G. Coco, V. Galli
Department of Physics
Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32, Milano 20133, Italy

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202506452>

© 2025 The Author(s). Advanced Functional Materials published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/adfm.202506452

S. Sabella
Translational Pharmacology Facility
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Morego, 30, Genova 16163, Italy

D. Russo
D3 PharmaChemistry
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Morego, 30, Genova 16163, Italy

D. Russo, M. Veronesi
Structural Biophysics Facility
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Morego, 30, Genova 16163, Italy

I. Penna, R. Scarpelli
Medicinal Chemistry and Technologies for Drug Discovery and Delivery
Facility
Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
Via Morego, 30, Genova 16163, Italy

control, computation, and provide synchronization signals. Therefore, edible logic circuits are required. Logic gates (such as NOT, NAND, XOR, etc.) execute Boolean operations and can be assembled to obtain circuits performing trigger signals as well as combinational and sequential logic. A few examples show the feasibility of this task using edible materials.^[7,8] Yet, either they are not integrated circuits^[7] or do not go beyond the demonstration of a simple logic gate.^[8] In all cases, the building blocks are electrolyte-gated organic field-effect transistors (EGOFETs), which have been proposed as an effective strategy to meet the low voltage operation required by edible electronics for both safety reasons and compatibility with edible energy sources.^[9,10]

The functional materials required for edible electronics can be selected in the first place from a pool of food derivatives and additives approved for consumption by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the American Food and Drug Administration (FDA), with specific acceptable daily intake (ADI) values. Materials commonly present in food, such as cellulose, starch, albumen, or coating agents like shellac and beeswax, have insulating properties and have been successfully employed as substrates, dielectric, and insulating layers in edible electronic components.^[8,9,11,12] Metals such as gold and silver, used in the food industry, for example for cakes decorations, serve as electronic conductors to fabricate electrodes, as well as activated carbon-based formulations, while ion-rich solutions serve as electrolytes.^[7,8,13] Regarding semiconductors, on the one hand, there is ongoing research on the electronic and charge transport properties of pigments and dyes found in food or approved for ingestion.^[14–17] Another strategy involves assessing the edibility of already well-known organic semiconductors. Poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT) is a benchmark biocompatible conjugated polymer with established electronic properties, making it suitable for application in transistors.^[18,19] It has been largely exploited for bioorganic interfaces, with no cytotoxic activity reported.^[19–21] Its compatibility with edible materials to deliver working transistors has already been proven,^[7,8] but a toxicity profile for transistors ingestion is completely missing.

This work introduces a potentially edible, fully printed coplanar logic family operating at 0.7 V, demonstrating NOT and NAND logic gates and a ring oscillator. Inkjet printing was chosen as a fabrication technique, allowing low-cost, low-temperature, and versatile deposition. For this purpose, inkjet printable solutions have been formulated for the electrodes, the semiconductor, and the passivation layer. An electrolyte-gated transistor based on edible materials has been optimized for integration in logic circuits, starting from a previous work,^[8] through the introduction of an edible passivation layer for the electrodes to reduce the leakage current and the implementation of a coplanar gate to ease the integration in more complex circuits. P3HT was used as a semiconductor for its reliable electronic properties and its compatibility with inkjet printing. To preliminarily evaluate the potential edibility of the fabricated transistor, we exploited an in vitro digestion assay that simulates the digestive conditions of the oro-gastro-intestinal (OGI) tract. The digested products were used for integrity tests on an intestinal cell epithelium using an in vitro cellular model, showing no cellular alteration.

The compatibility of the logic family with an edible rechargeable battery was also verified, effectively demonstrating the first

integration between edible energy sources and potentially edible electronic circuits.

This work represents the first step towards realizing food-based integrated logic circuits that could be safely used on devices in contact with food, inside the human body, or incorporated into more complex systems such as edible robots and robotic food.

2. Chitosan-Gated Transistors with Coplanar Gate

In this section, the fabrication and electrical characterization of chitosan-gated field-effect transistors (FETs) with a coplanar gate are illustrated. The coplanar architecture was chosen to enable easier integration of transistors in circuits. Ethyl cellulose (EC), approved as a food additive (E 462), proved to be an excellent substrate for edible electronics, being flexible and water insoluble.^[8,16]

Source and drain electrodes were inkjet printed on an EC film in an interdigitated structure ($L = 50 \mu\text{m}$ and $W = 10\,000 \mu\text{m}$) using a water-based gold ink that allows conductive lines with low-temperature drying without the need for actual sintering.^[8] The gate was printed on the side with the same gold ink. To allow the largest voltage drop at the electrolyte/semiconductor interface, the gate area was set to be five times larger than the active channel area.^[22] To reduce the leakage current, a shellac (E 904) ink was formulated and then inkjet-printed for passivation on the electrodes area that would otherwise be exposed to the electrolyte, as depicted in **Figure 1a–c**. A P3HT-based ink was deposited on the channel area by inkjet printing. Finally, a chitosan-based electrolyte, whose use in EGOFET was previously assessed with a top gate configuration,^[8] was drop-cast on the device to cover both the channel area and the gate, as shown in **Figure 1b** and **Figure S1** (Supporting Information). P3HT has never been tested for toxicity upon ingestion, but is considered here as candidate material for safe-to-ingest devices on the basis of its very well-known electronic properties, its printability and its proven biocompatibility, as widely documented in the literature where P3HT was exploited for the realization of bioorganic interfaces, with no cytotoxic effects evidence for several cell cultures.^[19–21] The amount of P3HT per transistor is $\approx 170 \text{ ng}$, less than 0.01% of the total mass of the transistor (calculation is reported in the Supporting Information). Details on the materials are given in the Supporting Information, while the fabrication steps are described in the Experimental Section.

Figure 1d,e show the typical I - V transfer and output characteristics of the printed chitosan-gated transistors: they demonstrate the field-effect behavior from linear ($V_{ds} = -0.1 \text{ V}$) to saturation regime ($V_{ds} = -0.7 \text{ V}$) for absolute gate voltages lower than 0.7 V. Considering the normalization for the geometrical parameters and the difference in applied voltages, the curves are comparable to those reported in a previous work by Sharova et al.^[8] for a similar transistor but fabricated with a silver gate inkjet-printed on top of the chitosan electrolyte. The threshold voltage V_{th} and the mobility-capacitance product $\mu_{sat} C$, extracted for $V_{ds} = -0.7 \text{ V}$ as explained in the Supporting Information, are -0.25 V and $0.094 \mu\text{F V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This comparison shows that the coplanar architecture maintains good electrical performance. The maximum ON current does not exceed a few μA , which not only is a safe value for application in ingestible devices as it is 3 orders of magnitude lower than current values that could cause injuries,^[23] but

Figure 1. Scheme of lateral a) and top b) view of the transistor. Ethyl cellulose (grey), gold (orange), shellac (yellow), semiconductor (purple), electrolyte (light blue). c) SEM image of the transistor, edited to highlight the different materials. d) Transfer I - V curve (average and standard deviation over 14 samples). The dashed line represents the gate leakage current I_{gs} as a function of V_{gs} for all the V_{ds} values. e) output I - V curve (average over 14 samples).

also produces a low static power consumption when used in logic gates operated below 1 V. Figure S3 (Supporting Information) shows the effect of the shellac passivation layer in reducing the leakage current and increasing the ON/OFF current ratio, especially at low operation voltages. The ON/OFF current ratio is in the order of 10^3 , which is suitable for proof-of-principle logic circuits since it ensures a sufficient distinction between high and low logic states.

3. Simulation of Human Ingestion of the Transistors and Impact on in Vitro Intestinal Cell Epithelium Model

The absence of toxicity data related to P3HT ingestion prompted us to apply a cascade dissolution assay in sterility conditions to obtain the first relevant data regarding eventual adverse effects of transistors ingestion on an epithelial tissue model.^[24] Initially developed for estimating the bioaccessibility of contaminants in soil and foods,^[25,26] the adopted cascade dissolution assay has recently been established as a useful in vitro tool with the potential to be predictive of biotransformation (e.g., dissolution/degradation, changes of size and surface charge) of ingested colloidal nanoparticles and pigments when digested in simulated OGI compartments.^[24,27,28] It applies fixed volume ratios

(e.g., among the amount of intaken products with or without food and saliva, gastric, pancreatic juices, and bile) and transit times that approximatively reflect the human physiology (i.e., stomach emptying time, concentration of secreted bile, etc.).^[26] The assay was applied to increasing numbers of transistors (0, 1, 5, 10) that were sequentially incubated in the simulant OGI compartments before a chewing step (Figure 2a). The resulting suspensions of digestive juices were centrifuged for clearing from debris, and the supernatants were exposed as digested samples on an epithelial tissue model based on a differentiated Caco-2 cell monolayer (Figure 2b). After 24 hours of incubation, the membrane integrity of the intestinal layer was assessed by measuring the Trans-Epithelial Electrical Resistance (TEER). Results (Figure 2c) indicated that the digested samples (i.e., conditioned intestinal juices) do not alter TEER values, providing a preliminary indication that the integrity of the cellular layer is preserved at the applied experimental conditions. Untreated intestinal juice (vehicle) was used as control not affecting cell viability. We can speculate that P3HT transistors, in conditions simulating digestion in the OGI tract, do not release any toxic soluble constituent compounds that may alter the cellular membrane integrity, or that these are at concentrations that did not exert any toxicity. These results suggest a short-term in vitro biocompatibility of the tested transistors. More in-depth tests, such as long-term ingestion effects, metabolic pathways, and potential bioaccumulation, will

Figure 2. a) Schematic of cascade in vitro digestion assay: upon a chewing step, increasing numbers of transistors (0, 1, 5, 10) were digested for 245 minutes at fasted conditions in simulant OGI compartments (saliva, stomach, and intestine), following a procedure as described in Di Cristo et al.^[24] b) Schematic illustrating the process of obtaining simulant intestinal juices pre-treated with chitosan-gated P3HT transistors, referred through the text as conditioned intestinal juices or digested samples, for cell culture experiments on Caco-2 monolayer. c) Cellular membrane integrity assay by TEER %. Results indicate that conditioned simulant intestinal juices, pre-treated with P3HT transistors, did not affect the TEER % of the cellular membrane at any of the concentrations tested (one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's posthoc test $p < 0.05$ versus Veh, $n = 30$).

in future allow to conclude about the complete edibility of the system.

4. Logic Gates

4.1. Inverter (NOT Gate)

A unipolar NOT gate was implemented using the transistor illustrated in the first section, acting as the pull-up network, and a matched resistor as the pull-down network. The resistor was fabricated on an EC substrate, printing interdigitated gold electrodes and P3HT on top of it. The conductivity of the pristine semiconductor was exploited to deliver, after proper dimensioning, a matched resistance in the order of $\approx 2 \text{ M}\Omega$ (Figure S5, Supporting Information). Since both the transistor and the resistor use the same material and techniques, a monolithic fabrication is possible, favoring the realization of integrated circuits. To characterize the NOT gate, a supply voltage $V_{dd} = 0.7 \text{ V}$ was applied. A voltage sweeping from 0 V to 0.7 V and back to 0 V was applied at the input V_{in} while measuring the output voltage V_{out} . The voltage transfer characteristic (VTC) curve of the NOT gate is reported in Figure 3a, with a quasi rail-to-rail V_{out} spanning over almost the entire voltage range ($\Delta V_{out}/\Delta V_{in} = 94\%$), low hysteresis ($0.014 \pm 0.004 \text{ V}$, as defined in Supporting Information) and good symmetry. The inversion point, which is the V_{out} at $V_{in} = V_{dd}/2$, is $\approx 0.35 \text{ V}$. The noise margins high NM_h and low NM_l (defined in Supporting Information) are 0.18 V and 0.25 V, respectively, ensuring sufficiently reliable operation in the presence of electrical noise and device to device variation. The plot in Figure 3b shows the gain of the fabricated edible inverters, with a peak value of 3.5 occurring approximately at half the input

voltage range. Figure 3c shows that the fabricated logic inverter responds well to a train of pulses at the input. The propagation delays $t_{p,LH}$ and $t_{p,HL}$ of the device can be extracted from this measurement, obtaining $0.04 \pm 0.01 \text{ s}$ and $0.13 \pm 0.01 \text{ s}$, respectively (extraction details in Supporting Information and Figure S6, Supporting Information). In this measurement, the capacitive load of the logic inverter is in the range of 10 to 30 pF, corresponding to the parasitic capacitance of the passive probes adopted and of the input of the Semiconductor Parameter Analyzer. If the RC of the circuit was the limiting factor, knowing the equivalent resistance R_{on} of the transistor ($\approx 90 \text{ k}\Omega$, extraction in Supporting Information) and the load resistance R , the propagation delays at 50% of the range $t_{p,LH}$ and $t_{p,HL}$ would be in the order of 0.6–1.8 μs and 15–45 μs , respectively (calculation details in Supporting Information). This huge discrepancy with the experimental data indicates that the dynamic response of the inverter is not limited by the load capacitance, but rather to an intrinsic switching time. This non-ideality can be tentatively explained by considering that the response of the EGOFETs to a change in the input voltage is subjected to the mobility of the ions in the electrolyte and the formation of the electric double layer.

4.2. NAND Gate

The same transistor was employed to realize a unipolar NAND gate. NAND gates represent a complete Boolean family: they can be arranged to perform potentially any logic operation, from simple AND and OR functions to memory cells and processors.^[29] The chosen configuration comprises two p-type transistors connected in parallel, and then in series with a resistor. The inputs

Figure 3. a) VTC of the fabricated unipolar inverter (average and standard deviation over 12 samples). b) Derivative curve of VTC to extract gain of the fabricated unipolar inverter (average and standard deviation over 12 samples). c) V-t plot of V_{in} (pink) and the corresponding V_{out} (purple) to show the time response to an impulse train of the fabricated unipolar inverter.

are applied to the gates of the transistors, and the output is taken from the common drain of the transistors (Figure 4a). As for the inverter in the previous section, the transistors and the resistor were fabricated by inkjet printing to obtain an integrated circuit. This NAND gate operates at a supply voltage of 0.7 V, as the described transistor and NOT gate. As inputs V_A and V_B , two square waves were used, with amplitude 0.7 V and frequency 0.1 Hz and 0.2 Hz, respectively (Figure 4c). In this way, the output voltage (V_{out}) for all combinations of inputs was obtained.

Figure 4c shows that V_{out} is low when both inputs are high, while it remains high for any other combination of V_A and V_B , demonstrating the correct behavior of the fabricated NAND gate. The output voltage operation is quasi rail-to-rail, with a minimum of ≈ 0.05 V and a maximum of ≈ 0.68 V. Propagation delays $t_{p,HL}$ and $t_{p,LH}$ for the NAND gate are 0.24 ± 0.04 s and 0.06 ± 0.01 s, respectively (extraction details in Supporting Information). The same discussion on the propagation delay introduced in the previous section applies.

5. Ring Oscillator

The demonstrated transistors were finally employed to realize a ring oscillator, as a representative circuit serving synchronization or timing functions in future edible systems. The circuit was fabricated by monolithically integrating three unipolar inverters connected in a ring configuration as shown in Figure 5a,b. Figure 5c shows the output voltage V_{out} of the ring oscillator as a function of time when $V_{dd} = 0.7$ V: V_{out} oscillates between 0.17 V and 0.59 V at a frequency of 1.32 Hz. The experimental oscillation frequency is comparable to the theoretical one of 1.96 Hz, calculated starting from the experimentally measured propagation delays of the inverters (details in the Supporting Information). Figure S7 (Supporting Information) shows a first assessment of the operability of the ring oscillator kept in air without encapsulation for 10 days.

Considering the fabricated circuit for the ring oscillator, the amount of edible materials per circuit represents 99% of the total

Figure 4. a) Circuitual scheme of a NAND gate in unipolar configuration. b) Picture of the gold paths of two NAND gates. c) V-t plots of the two inputs V_A and V_B (pink) and the corresponding output V_{out} (purple).

Figure 5. a) Circuitual scheme of a ring oscillator with unipolar p-type architecture. b) Picture of the fabricated ring oscillator. c) V_{out} as a function of time of the ring oscillator when biased with $V_{dd} = 0.7$ V.

weight (28.5 mg). The remaining 1% is mostly represented by inert metal used for the electrodes (260 μg). The biocompatible semiconductor, which was initially assessed through the cascade in vitro digestion assay, is present only in traces, in the range of micrograms (0.01% of the total circuit weight; **Table 1**).

6. Compatibility with Edible Energy Sources

The logic gates and the ring oscillator reported so far were powered by benchtop instruments to prove their correct functionality. However, these circuits are thought to be used in food labels and smart pills, as the drug release monitoring edible pill envisioned by Lamanna et al.,^[36] and in this context they would require a local power source, such as a battery. An edible rechargeable battery has been recently reported: it is made using only food additives and food derivative materials and can provide 20 μAh at ≈ 0.7 V.^[9,10] For a full description of the fabrication procedure of the edible battery, please refer to Galli et al.^[10] This voltage is compatible with the operating voltage of the fabricated logic gates and circuit, so the edible battery was tested as a power source.^[10] **Figure 6a** shows the performance of the NOT gate when it is powered by the edible battery and a voltage V_{in} sweeping between 0 and 0.7 V is applied to the gate. Similarly, **Figure 6b** shows the measured V_{out} of the fabricated ring oscillator when it is powered by the edible battery, as virtually represented in **Figure 6c**. The performance is comparable to that obtained when V_{dd}

was supplied by an external source, proving that the fabricated logic circuits can be successfully powered by an edible energy source.

7. Conclusion

This work presents a unipolar fully-printed logic family fabricated with non-toxic materials, comprising food-derived materials and an organic biocompatible semiconductor. The logic family is based on a chitosan-gated transistor, with a coplanar design to favor integration in circuits. The transistor also features a printed shellac-based passivation layer that reduces by an order of magnitude the leakage current due to direct contact between the electrodes and the electrolyte. A biocompatible polymer, P3HT, was used as a semiconductor. The chitosan-gated P3HT transistors were digested in vitro following a cascade dissolution assay and the pre-conditioned intestinal juices were exposed to Caco-2 cells monolayer. The integrity of the cellular membrane was not altered, suggesting the short-term biocompatibility of the fabricated devices and laying the foundation for future assessment of their potential edibility. The logic family is composed of NOT and NAND logic gates operating at 0.7 V with quasi rail-to-rail output. As a proof-of-concept of future edible circuits, an integrated ring oscillator providing a stable output at a frequency up to 1.32 Hz was demonstrated. The compatibility of the logic gates with edible energy

Table 1. Estimated amounts of materials per ring oscillator with the corresponding ADI value and EFSA E value. Dose of P3HT per transistor: 170 ng. Dose of P3HT per resistor: 745 ng.

Material [E number]	Dose per ring oscillator	ADI	Refs.
Ethyl cellulose (E 462)	26 mg	660/900 mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	[30]
Printed gold	0.26 mg	N/A	[31]
Shellac (E 904)	1.3 μg	4 mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	[32]
P3HT	2.7 μg	N/A	[33]
Chitosan	0.6 mg	N/A (food)	–
Glycerol (E 422)	1.2 mg	1–2 mg kg ⁻¹ day ⁻¹	[34,35]

sources was also demonstrated,[>] representing the first integration between a battery and logic circuits fabricated using edible materials.

While further toxicity studies upon ingestion will be required in future, as well as an optimization of the propagation delays and frequencies towards real-time monitoring applications, this logic family lays the foundation for the realization of printed integrated edible logic circuits that would perform computational tasks in future edible systems, such as GI tract monitoring pills, food labels, and edible robots. The materials selection makes this platform safe for ingestion without the need for recollection, while the fabrication technique, inkjet printing, makes it scalable and suited for the low temperature required by the perishable edible materials.

8. Experimental Section

Gold ink was purchased from C-ink Ltd. Poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT, regioregularity $\geq 90\%$, $M_w = 20 - 45$ kDa), EC powder (48.0-49.5% (w/w) ethoxyl basis), chitosan powder (low molecular weight), shellac wax-free, glycerol, acetic acid, ethanol, terpineol, chlorobenzene (CB), 1,2 dichlorobenzene (oDCB) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Edible Substrate Preparation: To fabricate the ethyl cellulose film used as a substrate, a 2% w vol⁻¹ solution of ethyl cellulose in ethanol was cast in a glass Petri dish ($\varnothing 9.5$ cm), let dry in the oven overnight at 60 °C and then peeled off with water. The ethyl cellulose films were flipped, exposing the side that was in contact with the Petri dish, which was characterized by a lower roughness. To flatten the films and ease the fabrication, they were attached to microscope glass slides by spreading a thin layer of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) and heating at 90 °C for 10 minutes. Right before inkjet printing, the films were treated with oxygen plasma (20 W for 1 min) to make the surface more hydrophilic.

Transistor Fabrication: Inkjet printing was carried out using a Fujifilm Dimatix DMP2850 with a Samba cartridge. Source/drain/gate electrodes were fabricated as interdigitated electrodes ($L = 50$ μm , $W = 10\,000$ μm) by inkjet printing gold ink (20 μm drop spacing, 1 layer, platen temperature 60 °C) followed by 30 min at 120 °C to improve the gold path conductivity. To fabricate the passivation layer, a printable ink was prepared by dissolving shellac in a blend of ethanol and terpineol, in a ratio of 1/1 vol vol⁻¹, at a concentration of 30 g L⁻¹, stirred overnight at 50 °C and filtered with a PTFE filter ($\varnothing 0.45$ μm). The shellac ink was inkjet-printed on the designated areas (20 μm drop spacing, 2 layers, platen at room temperature) and heated at 70 °C for 30 min to let the solvent dry. P3HT

was dissolved in a blend of oDCB and CB in a ratio of 1/3 vol vol⁻¹, at a concentration of 2.6 g L⁻¹. The semiconductor ink was inkjet-printed on the channel area (15 μm drop spacing, 2 layers, platen temperature 35 °C) and then annealed at 120 °C for 10 min in a N₂ filled glovebox. The electrolyte was prepared by dissolving chitosan in a 1% acetic acid aqueous solution at a concentration of 10 g L⁻¹ and stirring at room temperature overnight. Then, glycerol was added to the solution at 200% of the chitosan weight. A volume of 10 μL of solution was drop-casted on each transistor and let dry at 60 °C for 15 min. The thicknesses of shellac and P3HT were measured using mechanical profilometer (Alpha-step IQ, KLA Tencor) and were ≈ 90 nm and ≈ 65 nm, respectively. The thickness of gold was extracted from an AFM image of the gold electrodes and was ≈ 80 nm (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

Resistor Fabrication: The electrodes fabrication and semiconductor deposition followed the same methods described for the transistor, with $L = 25$ μm $W = 100\,000$ μm .

Device Characterization: The measurements of the transfer and output characteristics of the transistors, of the VTC of the NOT gates, and V-t characteristics of the NAND gates and the ring oscillators were performed in air using an Agilent B1500A Semiconductor Parameter Analyzer. The input V_A and V_B of the NAND gates were provided with Keysight 81150A Pulse Function Arbitrary Noise Generator. All the devices were measured in a room where the light was filtered below 500 nm.

Simulation of Digestion in the OGI tract of P3HT Transistors by Means of Cascade Dissolution Assay: Increasing numbers of transistors (0, 1, 5, 10) were cut and transferred in a mortar for gentle grinding. The fragmented transistors were collected in a 50 mL polypropylene tube to which simulated juices of saliva, stomach, and intestine/bile salts were added sequentially. The incubation time was selected to simulate the residence time of food in fasted conditions, according to Versantvoort et al.^[26] In particular, they were: 5 minutes in saliva, 120 minutes in the stomach, and further 120 minutes in the intestinal compartment. Concentrations and relative working volumes of applied chemicals and ingredients to formulate the simulant juices were reported in Di Cristo et al.^[24] All procedures performed for the cascade digestion assay were conducted in sterile conditions (e.g., consumables, reagents, and biological hood). The sterility of digested juices has been verified by incubating samples (1:5 diluted in complete cell culture medium) in Luria-Bertani (LB) medium overnight at 37 °C.

At the end of the digestion of the transistors (245 minutes of total residence time), the simulant intestinal juice, including the resulting debris, was centrifuged for 40 min at 3500 rpm, 4 °C to avoid the presence of macroscopic residues in the subsequent cellular experiments. The resulting supernatants (namely the simulant intestinal juices pre-treated with the chitosan-gated P3HT transistors) were applied as testing samples (referred to in the text as “conditioned intestinal juices or digested samples”) for cell culture experiments.

Figure 6. a) VTC of the inverter powered by the edible rechargeable battery. b) V_{out} (purple) of the ring oscillator powered by the edible rechargeable battery; in green the voltage provided by the edible battery. c) Demonstrative picture of the fabricated ring oscillator and the edible battery.

Cell Culture: Human colon epithelial (Caco-2) cells were purchased from ATCC (HTB-37). MEM with Earle's Salts medium, containing 1% final NEAA (Biowest). Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) buffer (calcium, magnesium, no phenol red) was purchased from Invitrogen. Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS) without calcium and magnesium and Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) were purchased from Merck. Culture flasks and Transwell inserts (polycarbonate membrane pore size 0.4 μm , diameter 12 mm) were purchased from Corning. Caco-2 cells were maintained in a 25 cm^2 culture flask at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO_2 . The complete medium was prepared by supplementing MEM with 20% (final) FBS. Cells were sub-cultured upon reaching $\approx 50\%$ confluence, changing the culture medium three times per week.

Permeability assay of conditioned intestinal juices (pre-treated with P3HT transistors): Following the SOP "Standard Operating Procedure" for evaluation of nanoparticles (NPs) impact on Caco-2 cell barrier model,^[37] Caco-2 cells were seeded at 4.5×10^4 cells cm^{-2} apically on Transwell® permeable cell culture inserts (pore size 0.4 μm) housed within 12 well plates and maintained for 21 days to allow full differentiation. 48 hours after the cell seeding on Transwell® inserts, cell medium was changed and reduced to 10% FBS. During the differentiation period, apical and basolateral media were changed every 3 days. Before starting the treatment, the integrity of epithelia has been checked by TEER measurement after 21 days of culture. Cell inserts were then incubated with conditioned intestinal juices (pre-treated with increasing amounts of P3HTs) or untreated intestinal juice (vehicle), diluted 1:5 in cell culture medium, for 24 hours. After the incubation time, TEER values were registered. All treatments were performed in three independent experiments. Pre- and post-treatment TEER measures of each layer were performed using a "chopstick electrode" connected to a Millicell Electrical Resistance System voltmeter (Millipore), maintaining the cells at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$ on a temperature-controlled heating plate. Only cell layers which returned a TEER value (expressed as $\text{Ohms } (\Omega) \times \text{cm}^2$) $> 200 \Omega \times \text{cm}^2$ were used. TEER values were presented as a percentage of control (vehicle-treated cellular layers). The measures were repeated three times for each insert, taking care to measure TEER in three different insert points, with a blank (cell free insert) resistance value subtracted according to the following equation:

$$\text{TEER} = [\Omega_{\text{cell monolayer}} - \Omega_{\text{filter (cell - free)}}] \times \text{filter area } (1.12 \text{ cm}^2) \quad (1)$$

TEER values registered were around $1000 \Omega \times \text{cm}^2$.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

G.C., V.F.A., V.G. and M.C. acknowledge the support of the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program through the project "ROBOFOOD" under Grant Agreement #964596. M.C. acknowledges the support of the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program through the project "ELFO" Grant Agreement #864299. V.F.A. acknowledges funding from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions (project name: "EDISENS", Grant Agreement #101105418) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program. This work is part of the "Technologies for Sustainability" Flagship program of IIT.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

edible electronics, electrolyte-gated transistors, inkjet-printing, organic electronics, sustainable electronics

Received: March 12, 2025

Revised: May 24, 2025

Published online:

- [1] H. Yousefi, H.-M. Su, S. M. Imani, K. Alkhalidi, C. D. M. Filipe, T. F. Didar, *ACS Sens.* **2019**, *4*, 808.
- [2] G. Cummins, *Adv. Drug Delivery Rev.* **2021**, *177*, 113931.
- [3] C. Steiger, A. Abramson, P. Nadeau, A. P. Chandrakasan, R. Langer, G. Traverso, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2019**, *4*, 83.
- [4] N. R. Misra, S. Kumar, A. Jain, in 2021 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Intelligent Systems (ICCCIS) **2021**, pp. 1032.
- [5] A. S. Sharova, F. Melloni, G. Lanzani, C. J. Bettinger, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2021**, *6*, 2000757.
- [6] D. Floreano, B. Kwak, M. Pankhurst, J. Shintake, M. Caironi, V. F. Annese, Q. Qi, J. Rossiter, R. M. Boom, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2024**, *9*, 589.
- [7] A. S. Sharova, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33*, 2103183.
- [8] A. S. Sharova, F. Modena, A. Luzio, F. Melloni, P. Cataldi, F. A. Viola, L. Lamanna, N. F. Zorn, M. Sassi, C. Ronchi, J. Zaumseil, L. Beverina, M. R. Antognazza, M. Caironi, *Nanoscale* **2023**, *15*, 10808.
- [9] I. K. Ilic, V. Galli, L. Lamanna, P. Cataldi, L. Pasquale, V. F. Annese, A. Athanassiou, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, *18*, 2211400.
- [10] V. Galli, V. F. Annese, G. Coco, P. Cataldi, V. Scribano, I. K. Ilic, A. Athanassiou, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2024**, *9*, 2400715.
- [11] M. Irimia-Vladu, E. D. Głowacki, G. Schwabegger, L. Leonat, H. Z. Akpinar, H. Sitter, S. Bauer, N. S. Sariciftci, *Green Chem.* **2013**, *15*, 1473.
- [12] G. Konwar, S. Rahi, S. P. Tiwari, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2023**, *15*, 35261.
- [13] Y. J. Jo, H. Kim, J. Ok, Y. J. Shin, J. H. Shin, T. H. Kim, Y. Jung, T. il Kim, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 1909707.
- [14] C. S. Boon, D. J. McClements, J. Weiss, E. A. Decker, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* **2010**, *50*, 515.
- [15] A. Singh, T. Mukherjee, *Mater. Adv.* **2022**, *3*, 1341.
- [16] E. Feltri, P. Mondelli, B. Petrović, F. M. Ferrarese, A. Sharova, G. Stojanović, A. Luzio, M. Caironi, *Adv. Sci.* **2024**, *11*, 2404658.
- [17] O. A. Hamad, R. O. Kareem, P. K. Omer, *J. Chem. Rev.* **2024**, *6*, 39.
- [18] J. Zaumseil, in *P3HT Revisited—From Molecular Scale to Solar Cell Devices* (Ed: S. Ludwigs), Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, **2014**, pp. 107–137.
- [19] E. Zucchetti, M. Zangoli, I. Bargigia, C. Bossio, F. Di Maria, G. Barbarella, C. D'Andrea, G. Lanzani, M. R. Antognazza, *J. Mater. Chem. B* **2017**, *5*, 565.
- [20] G. Scarpa, A. L. Idzko, S. Götz, S. Thalhammer, *Macromol. Biosci.* **2010**, *10*, 378.
- [21] C. Tortiglione, M. R. Antognazza, A. Tino, C. Bossio, V. Marchesano, A. Bauduin, M. Zangoli, S. V. Morata, G. Lanzani, *Sci. Adv.* **2017**, *3*, 1601699.
- [22] S. P. White, K. D. Dorfman, C. D. Frisbie, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, *120*, 108.
- [23] I. E. Commission, Effects of Current on Human Beings and Livestock. Part 1, General Aspects, International Electrotechnical Commission **2005**.
- [24] L. Di Cristo, J. G. Keller, L. Leoncino, V. Marassi, F. Loosli, D. A. Seleci, G. Tsiliki, A. G. Oomen, V. Stone, W. Wohlleben, *Nanoscale Adv.* **2024**, *6*, 798.

- [25] A. G. Oomen, C. J. M. Rompelberg, M. A. Bruil, C. J. G. Dobbe, D. Pereboom, A. Sips, *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* **2003**, *44*, 281.
- [26] C. H. M. Versantvoort, A. G. Oomen, E. Van de Kamp, C. J. M. Rompelberg, A. J. A. M. Sips, *Food Chem. Toxicol.* **2005**, *43*, 31.
- [27] C. Carnovale, D. Guarnieri, L. Di Cristo, I. De Angelis, G. Veronesi, A. Scarpellini, M. A. Malvindi, F. Barone, P. P. Pompa, S. Sabella, *Nanomaterials* **2021**, *11*, 1587.
- [28] S. M. Usmani, S. Bremer-Hoffmann, K. Cheyns, F. Cubadda, V. I. Dumit, S. E. Escher, V. Fessard, A. C. Gutleb, T. Léger, Y. Liu, *EFSA Support. Publicat.* **2024**, *21*, 8826E.
- [29] M. D. Ciletti, M. M. Mano, in *Digital Design*, Prentice-Hall, Hoboken **2007**.
- [30] M. Younes, P. Aggett, F. Aguilar, R. Crebelli, A. Di Domenico, B. Dusemund, M. Filipič, M. Jose Frutos, P. Galtier, D. Gott, U. Gundert-Remy, G. Georg Kuhnle, C. Lambré, J. C. Leblanc, I. T. Lillegaard, P. Moldeus, A. Mortensen, A. Oskarsson, I. Stankovic, P. Tobbyack, I. Waalkens-Berendsen, M. Wright, A. Tard, S. Tasiopoulou, R. A. Woutersen, *EFSA J.* **2018**, *16*, 05047.
- [31] *EFSA J.* **2016**, *14*, 4362.
- [32] M. Younes, G. Aquilina, L. Castle, G. Degen, K. Engel, P. Fowler, M. J. Frutos Fernandez, P. Fürst, R. Gürtler, U. Gundert-Remy, T. Husøy, M. Manco, W. Mennes, P. Moldeus, S. Passamonti, R. Shah, I. Waalkens-Berendsen, M. Wright, P. Boon, R. Crebelli, A. Di Domenico, M. Filipic, A. Mortensen, R. Woutersen, H. Henk Van Loveren, G. Gagliardi, E. Mazzoli, F. Lodi, J. D. Rasinger, A. M. Rincon, et al., *EFSA J.* **2024**, *22*, 8897.
- [33] G. Scarpa, A. Idzko, S. Götz, S. Thalhammer, *Macromol. Biosci.* **2010**, *10*, 378.
- [34] M. Younes, G. Aquilina, L. Castle, K. H. Engel, P. Fowler, M. J. Frutos Fernandez, U. Gundert-Remy, R. Gürtler, T. Husøy, M. Manco, W. Mennes, P. Moldeus, S. Passamonti, R. Shah, I. Waalkens-Berendsen, D. Wölfle, M. Wright, K. Cheyns, M. Mirat, A. M. Rincon, P. Fürst, *EFSA J.* **2022**, *20*, 07353.
- [35] G. Cantore, B. Guidetti, M. Virno, *J. Neurosurg.* **1964**, *21*, 278.
- [36] L. Lamanna, P. Cataldi, M. Friuli, C. Demitri, M. Caironi, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **2022**, 2200731.
- [37] I. De Angelis, J.-P. Piret, E. Dumortier, "Standard Operating Procedure for NPs Crossing Caco-2 Cell Barrier," can be found under <https://www.rivm.nl/en/about-rivm/mission-and-strategy/international-affairs/international-projects/nanoreg> **2015**.